

Reaction of Polymerisation Initiators with Metal Salts and Metal Complexes in Solutions. Interaction of Potassium Monopersulphate with Copper(II) Salts and Copper(II)/Hydroquinone Couple

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The catalytic decomposition of KHSO_5 in presence of Cu^{2+} ions and $\text{Cu}^{2+}/$ phenol couples in aqueous medium (25-50°) is facile and follows first order kinetics ($k_{\text{Cu}^{2+}} = 0.192 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $k_{\text{HQ}} = 0.46 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $k_{\text{Cu}^{2+}/\text{HQ}} = 8.29 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$)

CuSO_4 /hydroquinone couple catalyses KHSO_5 decomposition, the rate obeying the following equation,

$$-\frac{d[\text{KHSO}_5]}{dt} = \beta k_d [\text{Cu}^{2+}]^{0.49} [\text{HQ}]^{0.98} [\text{KHSO}_5]^{1.16}$$

The catalytic efficiency of Cu^{2+} , HQ and Cu^{2+}/HQ couple has been established from kinetic and spectrophotometric data. The mechanism of KHSO_5 decomposition has been proposed and the activation energy and other thermodynamic parameters have been calculated

THE peroxy compounds, like organic peroxides, hydroperoxides and inorganic peroxy salts are known to undergo facile homolysis of the peroxy-linkage in the presence of a trace of metal salt impurities to yield free radicals¹⁻⁷, thereby finding wide applications as free radical initiators and/or curing agents for polymer and resin industries. Sheldon and Kochi⁸ noticed that the participation of a given metal ion in a free radical process is strongly influenced by factors such as the kind of ligand bound to the metal ion and the presence of complexing agents in the reaction systems. Barton *et al.*⁹⁻¹¹ observed that the rate of cumene hydroperoxide (CHP) decomposition by Cu^{2+} -acetate was strongly affected by the addition of complexing agents such as amino alcohols. Indicator and Sahani^{12,13} found that the rate of t-butyl hydroperoxide (t-BHP) decomposition was greatly accelerated by metal acetylacetonates and such reactions caused high rate of initiation in vinyl and diene polymerisation.

However, no such studies have been reported on the influence of metal salts, complexing agents and metal salt/complexing agent couples on the free-radical decomposition of potassium monopersulphate excepting a few preliminary reports from our group¹⁴⁻¹⁷. Kennedy and Stock¹⁸ used potassium monopersulphate for oxidation of a multitude of organic substrates for preparative purpose. Recently, we have been examining the influence

of various metal salts, complexing agents and metal salt/complexing agent couples on the rate of decomposition of KHSO_5 in order to evaluate the condition of its decomposition for a high rate of initiation in vinyl polymerisation and graft copolymerisation. Present report is one aspect of these studies.

Experimental

Potassium monopersulphate (99.8%) was gifted by Du Pont Co., U.S.A., and was used as such. Acrylonitrile, sulphuric acid, CuSO_4 , $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Cu}(\text{OAc})_2$, CuCl_2 , phenol, nitrophenols, cresols, o-chlorophenol, catechol, hydroquinone, resorcinol, pyrogallol, α -naphthol, β -naphthol and phenanthroline were of AnalaR grade.

Methods: Acrylonitrile (AN) was purified by standard method¹⁹. KHSO_5 solution (0.129 M) was prepared in triple-distilled water and was stored in a refrigerator. Visible spectra were taken in a Beckmann 25 spectrophotometer at $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$. Experiments were carried out in coloured stoppered reaction vessels. Cu^{2+} salts of appropriate concentration were separately taken and thermostated at the desired temperature for 1 h, after which the KHSO_5 solution of appropriate concentration was added to each reaction vessel. The course of the initiator decomposition was followed by cerimetry using ferroin as indicator. The experiment was repeated for different concentrations of Cu^{2+} salts

and of KHSO_5 for different temperatures. The studies were repeated for each phenol. The nature of the decomposition process was also studied by adding acrylonitrile (0.754 M) to the reference and the actual experimental systems separately before adding the initiator. Precipitates of polyacrylonitrile obtained was estimated gravimetrically and by average molecular weight determination from intrinsic viscosity data.

$$[\eta] = 3.335 \times 10^{-4} \times \overline{M}_w^{0.72} \text{ dl g}^{-1}$$

Results and Discussion

Decomposition of potassium monopersulphate (KHSO_5 , $2.58 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$) with various Cu^{2+} salts, like $\text{Cu}(\text{OAc})_2$, CuCl_2 , $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and CuSO_4 ($2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$) at 30° follows first order kinetics with rate constants (30°) 0.232×10^{-5} , 0.202×10^{-5} , 0.195×10^{-5} and $0.192 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively, showing no significant effect of the anions. Hence, detailed examination was carried out with CuSO_4 to determine the most efficient conditions for its use. Rate dependence on CuSO_4 concentration and temperature at constant $[\text{KHSO}_5]$ are given in Figs 2 and 3, respectively, and on KHSO_5 concentration and temperatures at constant $[\text{CuSO}_4]$ can be seen in Figs. 4 and 3, respectively. The increasing value of k_{obs} with increasing $[\text{Cu}^{2+}]$ is due to the increase in concentration of complex ion formed by interaction of the vacant d^0 -orbital of Cu^{2+} ion with the bridged peroxo orbital of KHSO_5^{2-} , which disproportionates readily. This complex formation between Cu^{2+} and KHSO_5 can also be seen from the visible spectra (Fig. 1).

Fig 1 Visible spectra of (a) $[\text{CuSO}_4] = 0.02 \text{ M}$ and (b) $[\text{CuSO}_4] = 0.02 \text{ M} + [\text{KHSO}_5] = 0.0129 \text{ M}$ or $[\text{CuSO}_4] = 0.02 \text{ M} + [\text{HQ}] = 0.02 \text{ M}$.

Increase of temperature increases the rate of interaction of Cu^{2+} with KHSO_5 followed by fast homolysis as shown by the k_{obs} value. From the Arrhenius plot (Fig. 3), the energy of activation (ΔE) and other thermodynamic parameters were

Fig 2

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\log [\text{Cu}^{2+}]$ at various temperatures in decomposition of KHSO_5 , catalysed by CuSO_4 ; $[\text{KHSO}_5] = 0.0129 \text{ M}$ and $[\text{Cu}^{2+}] = 0.25-125 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$: (○) 25° , (●) 30° , (⊙) 40° and (⊕) 50° .

Fig. 3. Arrhenius plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $1/T$ in decomposition of KHSO_5 catalysed by CuSO_4 ; $[\text{KHSO}_5] = 0.0129 \text{ M}$ and $[\text{Cu}^{2+}] = 25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$.

computed as $\Delta E = 41.0 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^\ddagger = -227.19 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, $\Delta H^\ddagger = 43.59 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta G^\ddagger = 114.68 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\log \beta = -19.13$ and $\log A = 0.38$. The decrease of k_{obs} with increasing $[\text{KHSO}_5]$ (Fig. 4) may be attributed to (i) formation of stable complex of Cu^{2+} with KHSO_5 thus resisting subsequent disintegration, (ii) the arrest of Cu^{2+} ions by the anions of monopersulphate. The activity of Cu^{2+} ion to interact with the orbital of the peroxo-bridge is, therefore, reduced and hence the rate of decomposition of KHSO_5 decreases.

Fig 4. Plots of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\log [KHSO_5]$ at various temperatures in decomposition of $KHSO_5$ catalysed by $CuSO_4$; $[CuSO_4] = 125 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $[KHSO_5] = 3.235 - 25.8 \times 10^{-3} M$: (○) 25, (●) 30, (⊕) 40 and (⊕) 50°.

Catalysis by Cu^{II} /phenolic couples: The effect of some complex forming phenols, like pyrogallol, α -naphthol, salicylaldehyde and hydroquinone ($2 \times 10^{-3} M$) on the first order rate constant (k_{obs}) of $KHSO_5$ ($2.58 \times 10^{-3} M$) decomposition were studied and rate constants were found to be 2.58×10^{-5} , 3.22×10^{-5} , 0.15×10^{-5} and 0.46×10^{-5} and $0.15 \times 10^{-5} s^{-1}$, respectively. Further, the initiator $KHSO_5$ was subjected to the action of the above phenolics in the presence of $CuSO_4$ ($2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$) at 30° and the rate constants were found to be 8.31×10^{-5} , 8.29×10^{-5} , 7.29×10^{-5} and $0.35 \times 10^{-5} s^{-1}$ for the couples Cu^{II}/α -naphthol, Cu^{II} /hydroquinone, Cu^{II} /pyrogallol and Cu^{II} /salicylaldehyde, respectively.

Comparison of the rate data indicates that addition of $CuSO_4$ solution ($2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$) to the reaction mixture containing HQ and $KHSO_5$ enhances the rate of decomposition of $KHSO_5$ by a factor of 18 and the rate is also nearly 40 times higher than that for $CuSO_4$ alone. With salicylaldehyde, pyrogallol and α -naphthol, the addition of $CuSO_4$ does not enhance the rate remarkably. It has, therefore been established that $CuSO_4$ /HQ couple is the most efficient in causing decomposition of $KHSO_5$. The catalytic decomposition of $KHSO_5$ by Cu^{II} is almost independent of the nature of anions, even in the presence of hydroquinone. The rate constants (30°) for the decomposition of $KHSO_5$ ($2.58 \times 10^{-3} M$) by various Cu^{II} salts ($2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$)/HQ ($2 \times 10^{-3} M$) couple

were found to be 8.59×10^{-5} , 9.04×10^{-5} , 9.24×10^{-5} and $8.76 \times 10^{-5} s^{-1}$ for $CuSO_4$, $CuCl_2$, $Cu(OAc)_2$ and $Cu(NO_3)_2$, respectively.

Effect of hydroquinone concentration ($0.5 \times 10^{-3} - 3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) on the rate (30°) is depicted by the plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\log [HQ]$ in Fig. 5 which is a linear with unit (0.98) slope indicating first order dependence of the rate on $[HQ]$. The enhancement of the rate may be due to the increase in the concentration of Cu^{II} /HQ complex, which catalyses $KHSO_5$ decomposition. The effect of $[CuSO_4]$ ($0.25 \times 10^{-3} - 75.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) (30°) is exhibited by the plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\log [Cu^{II}]$ in Fig. 5 which is linear with slope of 0.5 indicating half order dependence of the rate on $[CuSO_4]$. The decreasing rate at high $[Cu^{II}]$ (beyond $12.5 M$) might be attributed to the formation of adduct between Cu^{II} ion and HSO_5^- anion, which is not affected by the Cu^{II} /HQ complex.

Fig 5. (a, ○) Plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\log [HQ]$ at 30° , in decomposition of $KHSO_5$ catalysed by Cu^{II} /HQ, $[Cu^{II}] = 25 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[KHSO_5] = 0.0258 M$ and $[HQ] = 0.5 - 3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$. (b, △) Plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\log [CuSO_4]$ at 30° in decomposition of $KHSO_5$ catalysed Cu^{II} /HQ, $[HQ] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[KHSO_5] = 0.0258 M$, $[CuSO_4] = 0.25 - 75.0 \times 10^{-3} M$

Effect of $[KHSO_5]$ ($0.322 \times 10^{-3} - 2.58 \times 10^{-3} M$) on the rate (30°) is given by Fig. 6 which is a linear plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\log [KHSO_5]$ with slope equal to unity (0.91) for the $KHSO_5$ range ($0.322 \times 10^{-3} - 0.645 \times 10^{-3} M$) indicating first order dependence of the rate on $[KHSO_5]$ upto $0.645 \times 10^{-3} M$, beyond which the rate decreases. Further, the rate (k_{obs}) was found to increase (8.06×10^{-5} to $17.37 \times 10^{-5} s^{-1}$) on increasing temperature from 25 to 40° at a given ($[Cu^{II}]$ ($2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$), $[KHSO_5]$) ($2.58 \times 10^{-3} M$) and $[HQ]$ ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$). From the Arrhenius plot (Fig. 7), the energy of activation (ΔE) and hence other thermodynamic parameters were

computed as $\Delta E = 40.33 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^\ddagger = -196.64 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, $\Delta H^\ddagger = 42.92 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta G^\ddagger = 104.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\log \beta = -17.44$ and $\log A = 2.97$.

Fig. 6. Plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\log [KHSO_5]$ at 30° in decomposition of $KHSO_5$ catalysed by Cu^{2+}/HQ ; $[CuSO_4] = 2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[HQ] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $[KHSO_5] = 0.322 - 2.58 \times 10^{-3} M$.

Fig. 7. Arrhenius plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $1/T$ in decomposition of $KHSO_5$ catalysed by Cu^{2+}/HQ ; $[CuSO_4] = 2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[KHSO_5] = 0.0258 M$ and $[HQ] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$.

Reaction mechanism :

Catalytic effect of Cu^{2+} ions : The decomposition of $KHSO_5$ by Cu^{2+} salts can be considered to proceed through the intermediate Cu^{2+} -monopersulphate complex (Fig. 1) which subsequently

decomposes and produces free radicals in subsequent steps. The order of decomposition reaction of $KHSO_5$ depends upon its concentration and the temperature, and lies between 0.07 to 0.67. At 40° in the range of 0.25×10^{-3} to $200 \times 10^{-3} M$ of $[Cu^{2+}]$, the observed order is 0.33 (Fig. 2). This inhibition with increasing $KHSO_5$ concentration (Fig. 4) indicates increasing salt formation with Cu^{2+} ions, thus preventing interaction with $Cu D^0$ orbital.

The free radical nature of the reaction is evident from acrylonitrile polymerisation to polyacrylonitrile, with average molecular weight ($\bar{M}_w$), 8.5×10^4 .

The following reaction mechanism has been proposed to interpret the above results,

The rate of $KHSO_5$ decomposition can be expressed as follows,

$$-\frac{d[KHSO_5]}{dt} = k_a \beta [Cu^{2+}]^x [KHSO_5]^y, \quad (1)$$

$$x : y = 1 : 2 = 0.5 : 1$$

$$-\frac{d[KHSO_5]}{dt} = k_a \beta [Cu^{2+}]^{0.5} [KHSO_5]^{1.0} \quad (2)$$

The rate equation (2) holds good at moderate $CuSO_4$ and $KHSO_5$ concentrations.

Catalysis by Cu^{2+}/HQ couple : It is noticed that $CuSO_4/HQ$ couple is an efficient catalyst for $KHSO_5$ decomposition, although the maximum activity is concentration dependent and also prone to thermal action. Further, in the three-component reaction, $CuSO_4/HQ/KHSO_5$, the rate with respect to the reacting components has been observed to be 0.49, 0.98 and 1.2, respectively. This results can be interpreted by considering an intermediate formation of an unstable complex between $[Cu(H_2O)_6]^{2+}$ species, existing in aqueous solution with HQ and $KHSO_5$ by successive displacement of water molecules. The formation of complex between Cu^{2+} and phenols have been identified²⁵⁻²⁷.

The addition of further ligand to complex-I is difficult, because of Jahn-Teller effect. The complex then disintegrates into various products where one KHSO_5 molecule and HQ on one side of the plane are active to react.

All the above processes lead to the following rate expression,

$$-\frac{d[\text{KHSO}_5]}{dt} = (\beta_1 + \beta_2) k_d [\text{Cu}^{2+}]^{1/2} [\text{KHSO}_5]^1 [\text{HQ}]^{1.0} \quad (3)$$

According to our observed rate and taking $(\beta_1 + \beta_2 = \beta)$, equation (1) is changed to

$$-\frac{d[\text{KHSO}_5]}{dt} = \beta k_d [\text{Cu}^{2+}]^{0.49} [\text{HQ}]^{0.98} [\text{KHSO}_5]^{1.15} \quad (4)$$

Equations (3) and (4) are the same, taking into account the experimental and graphical errors.

We can, therefore, conclude that in the reaction of a polymerisation initiator, potassium persulphate, with Cu^{2+} salts and their phenol complexes especially hydroquinone, the peroxy salt undergoes ready decomposition to free radicals through the intermediate formation of unstable complexes. Similar reactions to free radicals not involving intermediate complex, also holds good in its reaction with phenols. But neither Cu^{2+} nor the phenols alone are significantly effective for KHSO_5 decomposition. However, Cu^{2+}/HQ couple in all molar proportions is quite effective catalyst to cause facile decomposition and the rates of decomposition

sharply increase by increasing their molar ratios. Hence, Cu^{2+}/HQ is a first catalyst for KHSO_5 decomposition to free radicals, that enhances the rate of initiation in vinyl polymerisation leading to polymers of high kinetic chain length. The novelty of the complex catalysed peroxide decomposition leading to high rate of initiation makes a compromise that chemical entities which are long since been recognised as retarders and/or inhibitor^{28,29} of radical addition reactions change their characteristics to accelerate such reactions when brought together in solution at appropriate molar ratios.

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